

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING (SMM) IN THE RESTAURANTS

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Annotation: *This article reveals the possibilities of using social media marketing tools. The author considers the use of social media marketing in the restaurant business. the author discusses the results of a study of the target group regarding the effectiveness of various social networks in order to disseminate information.*

Key words: *social media marketing, promotion, social networks, research, survey.*

Social media marketing (SMM) (also known as digital marketing and e-marketing) is the use of social media - the platforms on which users build social networks and share information - to build a company's brand, increase sales, and drive website traffic. In addition to providing companies with a way to engage with existing customers and reach new ones, social media marketing (SMM) has purpose-built data analytics that allow marketers to track the success of their efforts and identify even more ways to engage. The relevance of the article is determined by the fact that the tasks of the presence of a restaurant in social networks can be reduced to two: to form a loyal audience, as well as to get direct traffic to your establishment.

With over 80% of consumers reporting that social media especially influencer content significantly impacts buying decisions, marketers across industries are driving the evolution of social media marketing (SMM) from a stand-alone tool to a multipronged source of marketing intelligence on an increasingly important and growing audience¹.

The more targeted your social media marketing (SMM) strategy is, the more effective it will be. Hootsuite, a leading software provider in the social media management space, recommends the following action plan to build an SMM campaign that has an execution framework as well as performance metrics²:

- Align SMM goals to clear business objectives
- Learn your target customer (age, location, income, job title, industry, interests)
- Conduct a competitive analysis on your competition (successes and failures)
- Audit your current SMM (successes and failures)
- Create a calendar for SMM content delivery
- Create best-in-class content
- Track performance and adjust SMM strategy as needed

Based on the marketing research conducted by the authors using the means of filling out google-forms by respondents, it was found that more and more users choose a restaurant after studying reviews about it and viewing the site, but rather, the official page of the institution.

As shown by the content analysis on the research problem, today only catering establishments that have monopoly advantages can afford to abandon their online presence.

¹ Business Wire. [“Matter Survey Reveals Consumers Find Influencers More Helpful and Trustworthy than Brands During the Pandemic”](#)

² Hootsuite. [“How to Create a Social Media Marketing Strategy.”](#)

For example, the canteen at the university, which students are doomed to go to anyway due to lack of choice. However, for such a company, a group in social networks with active users will not be superfluous. After all, a formed loyal audience can react and respond to various marketing activities, including for free. Such subscribers at their level are ready to act as brand marketers - again, for free, or for a small fee. For example, draws of small presents for the number of reposts.

Social Media Marketing (SMM) - social media marketing is the promotion of goods and services in social networks, blogs, groups, forums that are perceived by marketing as social media.

SMM is aimed directly at the target audience, and has more in common with network PR than with advertising. Consumer attention can be bought with advertising, but trust cannot be bought, it must be earned. At the moment, the social media audience is comparable to the TV audience, but is more focused and responsive. The job of social media is that they, through direct and covert interaction, reach the target group of users.

Among the popular platforms that consumers use are not only the popular Facebook, Instagram and Twitter, but also the social Internet service and photo hosting Pinterest, the business social network LinkedIn, the Tumblr and Flickr microblogging services, YouTube and Vimeo video hosting, new video hosting formats Coub and Vine, as well as personal messengers WhatsApp, Viber and Telegram³.

No less important direction than maintaining pages in social networks is working with bloggers. Organizing events specifically for bloggers is a good strategy for generating positive feedback about your establishment or combating negative feedback. At such events, the restaurant can feed bloggers for free, talk about dishes and cuisine and ask them to leave honest reviews in return. Let's not forget about visualization.

Recently, video advertising is gaining more and more popularity on the Internet. However, the production of full-fledged videos is still quite expensive for most. A convenient alternative to full-length videos is the use of relatively new social media video formats such as Instagram Live, Facebook Stories and Instagram.

Each event is important and decisive for the development of the enterprise, using SMM. Social media promotion can bring great benefits to a restaurant, but with proper implementation and process management.

As platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram took off, social media transformed not only the way we connect with one another but also the way businesses are able to influence consumer behavior from promoting content that drives engagement to extracting geographic, demographic, and personal information that makes messaging resonate with users⁴.

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³ Лебедева Татьяна Евгеньевна, Прохорова Мария Петровна. “Возможности SMM в ресторанном бизнесе”
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⁴ [https://www.investopedia.com.Social-Media-Marketing-\(SMM\):-What-It-Is,-How-It-Works,-Pros-and-Cons](https://www.investopedia.com.Social-Media-Marketing-(SMM):-What-It-Is,-How-It-Works,-Pros-and-Cons).

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